

Stereotypes

Introduction

A stereotype is referred to a thought that might be adopted by different types of individuals about different types of doing things or performance of particular actions. It is important to understand that the particular belief that an individual carries might be correct and might not. The above mentioned definition of stereotype is a basic psychological definition of a stereotype. In the entire subject of psychology, there are different concepts and definitions that are present regarding stereotyping that further expand the definition of stereotyping. It is observed that some of the definitions of stereotyping may share some common aspects, while others may possess unique aspects that may further contradict or complement the other aspects in other different definitions (Schneider, pp. 108). The core focus of this paper is to share and discuss a stereotype and bias that is carried in my mentality and the ways in which my biasness may hurt a certain group towards which my biasness is targeted.

Discussion

The biasness that I carry in my cognition is towards the teenagers in the current society and it is also obvious that everyone might not think in the same way as I do. It is also not essential that everyone might think that my perception about the people of teenage group is right. It is believed by me that the teenagers in the present society are not seen to be serious towards their work and responsibilities and they always like to spend their time with friends in parties and other social gatherings. For me, the teenage boys and girls pose a reputation of being obnoxious,

mischievous, and foolish to some extent. Many people argue with me that it would not be appropriate for considering the teenage people of the modern society only to be mischievous and foolish. Many people believe that the teenage boys and girls are very intelligent and could do good works.

On the other hand, my perception about the teenage boys and girls remains the same. A core reason for this biasness is the difference between the time of my teenage and the teenage individuals of the present society. The facilities that the modern teenagers enjoy were not available to us. This made me more targeted and committed towards my responsibilities and academic studies. The teenage people of the modern society are mostly seen engaging themselves in mischievous activities and enjoying their lives through bad things and activities, which also make them distracted from their studies and their ultimate goal. It is further observed that the teenage boys and girls are also involved in drinking activities which usually occur at house parties (Budden, pp. 48). In addition to this, there are many cases which are seen to be involving sexual activities involving teenage boys and girls which further lead to negative and destructive circumstances.

These are the main reasons due to which a biased reputation is created for teenage boys and girls in my mind. It is very true that I was not involved in any of the bad activities in which the teenage boys and girls are involved today, so it automatically makes me against the activities of the teenagers. The people that have a good perception for the teenagers of the modern society pay attention to the intelligence and the creativity that the modern teenage people could bring in their work with the help of technology know how. One of the simplest ways of trying to change my perception about the teenagers of the modern society is to think about the positive works that could be done by the teenagers on the basis of the education that they are getting in the modern

education system. Merging my cognition and the positive thinking of the other people who have positive thinking about the modern teenagers could be a good way of changing my perception for the teenagers into a positive one.

A very important thought to be incorporated in this people is that the teenagers might also feel bad about the perception that I perceive about them because I am not the only one to have a such a perception about the teenagers; there might be others people as well (Cook, pp. 76). The teenage group might feel hurt in a way that they are not the only people who involve themselves in activities like party, drinking and other physical activities. There are also some teenagers who maintain a balance between their academic studies and the other extra activities that they engage themselves into. It is also observed that some teenagers are very sensitive with respect to the comments of their elders. In addition to this, some teenagers might also treat themselves in negative ways to give physical negativity to their bodies. These are the most significant ways through which my perception regarding the teenagers of the modern society could hurt them.

Conclusion

The above discussion has made my biasness or stereotyping about the people of teenage group in the modern society very clear along with the ways in which y perception could hurt the teenagers.

References

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